

**THERMO ACOUSTICAL INVESTIGATIONS OF MOLECULAR INTERACTIONS IN
ANTIBIOTIC NORFLOXACIN**

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ABSTRACT

A investigation of possible molecular interaction of antibiotic Norfloxacin is carried out to provide insight of molecular orbital (or) other calculation designed to elucidate electronic and conformational aspects of molecule are now used based on certain physical and bio-chemical properties. This is carried out through ultrasonic investigations at temperature 303K.

The ultrasonic velocity, density and co-efficient of viscosity were measured and the thermo acoustical parameters like adiabatic compressibility, acoustics Impedance, intermolecular free length and internal pressure were derived and these parameters describes the molecular interaction of aqueous Norfloxacin particularly the hydrogen bonding with the structural change of water molecules.

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